

Review Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Moisturising Cream Containing Coriander Leaves Extract

Ashwathi V. V., Ismail M., Mariyambi K. V., Nafeesath K. P., Shahala, Shamna K.

Rajiv Gandhi institute of pharmaceutical science and research, Trikaripur, kasaragod, Kerala

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ABSTRACT

The herbal moisturising cream with natural ingredients is more acceptable in public opinion than other chemical based formulation due to their safety and efficacy in maintaining protecting moisturising and lubricating the skin and also helps to smooth the skin. Aim and Objective: The aim of this investigation is to formulate and evaluate the moisturising cream containing coriander leave extract. The objective of the present work is to formulate herbal moisturising cream containing natural ingredients like coriander leaves, aloe vera and cucumber. Methods: The drug is extracted by the process of maceration. The in vitro antimicrobial activity is determined by agar well diffusion method by using Ampicillin as standard. The formulated moisturising cream is tested against lactobacillus for its activity. Result: The formulated herbal moisturising cream were evaluated to determine important physical characteristics such as homogeneity, ph, viscosity and spreadability. All in vitro evaluation of prepared moisturising cream showed better results. The developed formulation showed anti microbial activity against bacterial culture and produced a better zone of inhibition. Conclusion: The research proves that our herbal based moisturising cream formulation with natural ingredients is excellent as it gets in terms of performance.

INTRODUCTION

HERBAL MEDICINE

Herbal medicines are also known as herbal remedies, phytotherapeutic agents, Phytopharmaceuticals etc. are the oldest and still the most widely used system of medicine. Since ancient time it was used by man as the first line treatment for a majority of diseases. Due to its

natural origin and less side effects, herbal medicines still flourish and are finding remarkable acceptance in both developed and developing countries. Phytochemicals were used by the man for the treatment of various disease like microbial infections, cardiovascular disorders, carcinogenic complications, metabolic disorders etc. According

***Corresponding Author:** Mariyambi K. V.

Address: Rajiv Gandhi institute of pharmaceutical science and research, Trikaripur, kasaragod, Kerala

Email ✉: mariyambikv9@gmail.com

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to World Health Organization, it is determined that 80% of the world population only depends upon the herbal medicine for the treatment of various disease. Plant based medicine have become an important component of traditional system for healing in developing countries, which have also been an integral part of their history and culture. According to the current research, the use of herbal medicines is increasing throughout the world than that of conventional drugs by two to three times. Today the novel formulations are reported to have more significant advantages over conventional formulations which include enhancement of bioavailability, solubility, pharmacological activity, stability, Improved tissue macrophages distributions, sustained delivery, and protection from toxicity, physical and chemical degradation.

HERBAL COSMETICS

Herbal cosmetics are also referred to as natural cosmetics. Herbal cosmetics are the product, which are formulated by using various ingredients to form the base in which one or more herbal ingredients are used to provide defined cosmetics benefits. Herbal cosmetics are formulated by using various herbal extracts containing a wide range active principle such as alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, vitamins, amino acids, sugars, essential oil, enzymes etc. Herbal extracts are added to the formulation due to its several properties like anti-oxidant properties. The topical application of herbal extracts are also produces anti-inflammatory properties, hence herbal cosmetics are found to be better formulation than synthetic formulation.

SKIN COSMETICS

Skin cosmetics contain substances which enable the skin to function properly. Skin care is a routine daily procedure in many settings, such as skin that is either too dry or too moist, and prevention of dermatitis and prevention of skin injuries. The basic functions include cleansing, anti-drying, ultraviolet damage prevention, anti-oxidation but they can also clear up skin problems, have a whitening effect to combat skin ageing associated problems and prevents wrinkles, acne, etc.

MOISTURIZING CREAM

- Moisturizer is a cosmetic preparation used for protecting, moisturizing, and lubricating the skin.
- These are creams which restore water(moisture), to the stratum corneum.
- Water contained in the cream is lost by evaporation when the cream is applied to the body.
- Moisturizers are complex mixtures of chemical agents often occlusive help hold water in the skin after application, humectants attract moisture and emollient help smooth the skin.

ROLE OF MOISTURIZERS

- Moisturising action
- Anti-inflammatory action
- Antimicrobial action
- Antimitotic action
- Antipruritic action
- Protective action

MATERIALS AND METHODS

List of materials

Table no.1 plant material used for the development of formulation

SI No	Botanical Name	Source/ supplier	
1	Coriandrum sativum	Indoor ventures	
2	Cucumis sativus	Indoor ventures	
3	Aloe barbadensis	Indoor ventures	

Plant collection

Leaves of *Coriandrum sativum*, *Cucumis sativus*, *aloe barbadensis* was collected from Kasargod district, Kerala in the month of march 2024.

Authentication of plant material

The plant material was identified and authenticated by Dr. Subramanya prasad K M.SC,phd Assistant professor (Department Of Botany) Nehru Arts & Science college kanhangad

EXTRACTION

- Coriander leaves extraction is conducted by maceration
- Maceration is a simple extraction technique, used to extract active ingredients from a plant material using a solvent at room temperature.

Materials Required

1. Fresh coriander leaves
2. solvent (hydroethanolic)
3. mortar and pestle or a blender
4. glass jar or container with lid
5. filter paper or fine mesh strainer
6. collection vessel (beaker or flask)

Procedure

Preparation of coriander leaves

Coriander leaves is thoroughly washed with tap water and then allowed to dry at room temperature. The dried plant material was ground into powder and safely stored under later usage.

Maceration process

- Coriander leaves is dried and ground into a powder.

- Powder was transferred to a mortar and pestle to breakdown the contaminants.
- Powder was transferred into a conical flask or container

Adding the solvent

- 50 ml of hydroethanolic solvent is added to a conical flask containing coriander powder
- The container is sealed with lid to prevent the solvent from evaporating

Maceration time:

Coriander powder is placed in hydroethanolic for one week and occasionally agitated

Filtration

- After maceration period the mixture is filtered to separate the liquid extract from the coriander leaves residues.
- Filter paper or a fine mesh strainer is used to filter the mixture into a clean collection vessel

Collection and storage

- Filtered extract is collected in a beaker or conical flask.
- The extract is stored in a sealed container, preferably in a cool, dark place to maintain its stability and prevent degradation.

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

The extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect the various phytoconstituents such as carbohydrates flavonoids alkaloids saponins sterols and terpenoids

FORMULATION OF MOISTURIZING CREAM

Sl no	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	Functions
1	Coriander sativum	2g	6g	4g	Give colour and glow to the skin
2	Aloe vera	2g	4g	3g	sunburn, moisturiser the skin and manage skin condition such as acne
3	Cucumber	2g	5g	3g	Great source of hydration keep the skin healthy

4	Liquid paraffin	8.5ml	8.5ml	8.5ml	Lubricant
5	Beeswax	0.8g	0.8g	0.8g	Occlusive which increases the water content of skin
6	Stearic acid	14.5ml	14.5ml	14.5ml	Emulsifying and thickening agent
7	Cetyl alcohol	1.5g	1.5g	1.5g	Stabilising agent
8	Propylene glycol	3ml	3ml	3ml	Retains moisture in the skin and gets better absorption
9	Glycerine	4ml	4ml	4ml	Humectant
10	Triethanolamine	1ml	1ml	1ml	Emulsifier
11	Tween80	5g	5g	5g	Emulsification
12	Methyl paraben	0.1g	0.1g	0.1g	Preservative
13	Lemongrass oil	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml	Flavouring agent
14	water	Q.s 50ml	Q.s 50ml	Q.s 50ml	Solvent

PROCEDURE

Initially the oil phase-liquid paraffin, beeswax and stearic acid were weighed accurately melted in a china dish at 70 degree Celsius. Cetyl alcohol was melted in another china dish at same temperature and to that propylene glycol, glycerine, triethanolamine, tween 80, aloe vera gel and cucumber juice was added. Methyl paraben and coriander extract of suitable concentration was added in the aqueous phase with continuous stirring to dissolve the ingredients. The melted oil phase was added into the aqueous phase with constant stirring maintain the temperature at 35-40 degree Celsius resulting in a semisolid consistency. lemon grass oil was added to the formulation and evaluation parameters of the moisturising cream was carried out.

EVALUATION OF PREPARED CREAM FORMULATION

Physical evaluation

Physical parameters such as colour, odour and appearance was evaluated

Homogeneity

The developed cream was tested for homogeneity by visual inspection after the cream have been set in the container for their appearance and presence of any aggregates.

Determination of pH

Ph calibrated using std buffer solution. About 0.5g of the cream was weighed and dissolved in 50ml of distilled water in a beaker, and its pH was measured.

Viscosity

The measurement of viscosity of prepared cream from coriander extract was done with brook field viscometer. The reading was taken at 100 rpm using spindle no 6

Spreadability

Emolliency, slipperiness and amount of residue left after the application of cream was checked

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical analysis

Test	Present /Absent
Test for saponins	-
Test for terpenoids	+
Test for carbohydrates	+
Test for alkaloids	+
Test for tannins	+
Test for flavonoids	+
Test for sterols	+

Evaluation Of Moisturizing Cream

Physical Evaluation

Physical evaluation such as colour, odour, appearance were evaluated.

Parameters	Observation
Colour	White
Odour	Characteristics
Appearance	Pleasant
Nature	Homogenetic

Homogeneity

Formulation	Homogeneity
Control	Homogeneous
F1	Homogeneous

Determination Of pH

	F1	F2	F3
pH	6.95	6.97	6.99

Determination Of Spreadability

	F1	F2	F3
Spreadability	2.0625 cm/sec	2.0628 cm/sec	2.0627 cm/sec

Viscosity

	F1	F2	F3
Viscosity	2013.2cp	2425.3cp	2137.6cp

DISCUSSION

The present work is to develop topical formulation containing phytopharmaceuticals to be applied for the moisturizing effect. The main aim of study is to make topical preparation cream containing extract of coriander leaves of *Coriandrum sativum* for moisturizing activity.

- Preliminary phytochemical screening were performed by using solvents such as ethanol and result showed the presence of various phytoconstituents such as carbohydrates, flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, alkaloids and tannins.
- Maceration of plant material were performed using water as menstruum.
- The moisturising cream were formulated by using water extract of *Coriandrum sativum*.
- The physical parameters such as colour and appearance were observed and the result showed that developed moisturising cream was white in colour, pleasant in appearance and showed good homogeneity.
- The ph,spreadability,viscosity were also performed. The prepared moisturising cream showed good results.

CONCLUSION

Although there are many moisturising creams on the market, there is still a role for herbal creams as they are natural, safe to use, and either have no or very few side effects. The herb *Coriandrum sativum* is used to cure a variety of illnesses,

and it can serve as a significant platform for the development of reasonable, efficient, and safe medicines. Moreover, it is capable of acting as an antibacterial agent against *P. acne*. In this study, four formulations were prepared with different ingredient ratios, and their physicochemical properties were assessed. The UV light that is thought to cause skin conditions can be absorbed by coriander extract. The coriander extract's proven anti-solar activity demonstrates its significance in anti-solar formulations. The results of the tests for stability, pH, viscosity, spreadability, and skin irritation indicated that F3 is the optimum formulation and would serve as an excellent moisturising cream.

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